

Dating young lunar craters with a simulation model based on the precise counting of very small craters

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Introduction: The simulation model described herein combines a crater production function, based on crater counts on the ejecta blanket of Giordano Bruno, with erosion and obliteration processes. Craters smaller than 50 m in diameter have lifetimes of just a few tens to hundreds of Ma, depending on their diameter and the nature of the surface on which they are formed. Crater lifetimes L are believed to be proportional to crater diameter raised to the power P , where the value of P ranges from 1.2 to 1.6. In other words, $L = kD^P$.

Crater production function: Two overlapping images of the ejecta blanket south of Giordano Bruno craters, both taken under ideal illumination conditions, were counted automatically and only those craters matched across them were accepted [1].

Fig 1. Area counted at Giordano Bruno crater

The counts for each 0.5m diameter step between 3 m and 50 m were divided by 10 (assuming an age of 10 Ma for Giordano Bruno) and plotted as a CSFD. The values for >4 m, >10 m, >20 m and >30 m were then compared with those predicted from fireball counts on Earth (Figure 2) [2]. The meteoroid flux at the lunar surface is believed to be significantly higher at the apex of the Moon's motion around the Earth than it is at the antapex [3] (Figure 3). As Giordano Bruno is close to the antapex, any ages calculated for craters closer to the apex must be adjusted downwards, eg by 10% for North Ray and Tycho craters.

Fig. 2 Annual crater production vs predicted values

Fig. 3 Apex distance meteoroid flux variation

Crater erosion and obliteration: Even the very smallest craters continue to be recognisable for several tens of Ma, with very little obliteration by then. But after about 40 Ma the oldest and smallest ones start to be eroded away completely and counts reach a steady state. The time required to reach a steady state is critically dependent on diameter, the larger the crater the longer it will survive (Figure 4). Crater lifetimes also increase according to the power P that is needed to explain the crater count distribution [4]. As populations of the larger craters rise, the obliteration of smaller craters ("cookie cutting") becomes a more significant factor. Thereafter, populations increase more slowly and towards equilibrium.

The simulation model: In order to study the evolution of crater populations on the Moon, a simulated area of lunar surface is randomly bombarded with meteoroids (in 1 Ma steps) to create craters having sizes and counts in accordance with their production rates derived from the Giordano Bruno results.

Fig. 4 Crater accumulation by size and power P

A very large number of such simulations are carried out, with a large range of periods of time and exponent values P from 1.20 to 1.60, in steps of 0.01. Under these conditions, it was found that the scaling factor k could be set to a constant value of 1.1 for all sites. The results are then combined and sorted in order to find the best match(es) for each site.

Fig. 5 Simulation fit for Cone crater

The crater density histogram for Cone crater at the Apollo 14 landing site is shown in Figure 5, together with the six closest fits to densities across the full size range. The simulated ages range from 33 and 39 Ma and require P to be between 1.23 and 1.26. Applying the downward age adjustment required because of Cone's relative proximity to the apex (30% in this case), results in a reduced age for Cone of 26 ± 2 Ma, in agreement with its radiogenic age [6].

A number of other young, Copernican-age craters have been dated in the same way, the results being summarised in Figure 6. In the case of the youngest craters (such as Dawes) the P value is indeterminate.

Location	Latitude	Longitude	Diam (km)	P	Age (Ma)
Vaughan	41.5°N	188.3°E	3	-	6
Stevinus A	31.8°S	51.6°E	8	-	21
Dawes	17.2°N	26.4°E	18	-	26
Lalande	4.4°S	351.4°E	3	-	26 ± 1
Necho	5.3°S	123.2°E	4	-	32 ± 2
Cone	3.6°S	342.6°E	0.3	1.24	25 ± 2
Tharp	31.4°S	146.0°E	13	1.18	48 ± 2
North Ray	9.0°S	15.5°E	1	1.43	47 ± 4
Messier	1.9°S	47.7°E	10	1.40	53 ± 4
Messier A	1.9°S	47.7°E	10	1.48	55 ± 2
Proclus	16.1°N	47.5°E	28	1.39	65 ± 6
Euclides C	13.1°S	330.0°E	10	1.31	59 ± 4
Furrierius A	33.6°S	59.0°E	12	1.52	77 ± 4
Tycho	39.1°S	349.4°E	85	1.18	85 ± 7

Fig. 6 Simulated ages of some young lunar craters

After adjustment for the apex distance, the age determined for North Ray is consistent with its radiogenic age of 50 Ma and the age of 85 Ma determined for Tycho is the same as its absolute model age [5], providing strong evidence in favour of the 10 Ma age assumed here for Giordano Bruno crater. The craters Messier and Messier A appear to have been contemporaneous, supporting a double impact. Tharp is similar in age to North Ray, but required a much lower value for P to achieve a successful simulation.

The crater Dawes is not far from the Apollo 17 site in the Taurus Littrow valley. Its calculated age of 26 Ma is similar to the cosmic ray exposure ages of the Station 6 and 7 boulders at the foot of the North Massif, 22 and 28 Ma respectively [6], so it is tempting to suggest that ejecta from Dawes impacted the North Massif, which faces in that direction, and disturbed both boulders. Likewise, ejecta from Proclus crater about 65 Ma ago, may have been responsible for the formation of the South Massif landslide [7].

Another benefit of the simulation model comes from its ability to identify when craters of a given diameter reach an equilibrium density for different values of P (Figure 6). For example, with a P value of 1.5, 7 m craters reach 270 per sq km after 65 Ma, 15 m ones 14.1 per sq km after 125 Ma and 25 m ones 1.9 per sq km after 220 Ma [8].

k	P	7 m Ma dens	10 m Ma dens	15 m Ma dens	19 m Ma dens	25 m Ma dens	30 m Ma dens
1.1	1.1	20	96	30	21	40	4.2
1.1	1.2	25	121	40	29	65	7.8
1.1	1.3	40	158	50	39	85	9.3
1.1	1.4	60	210	70	54	105	11.8
1.1	1.5	65	270	95	72	125	14.1
1.1	1.6	75	353	125	97	235	23.4
						350	10.7
						380	3.3
						70	0.5
						95	0.9
						125	1.2
						210	1.9
						220	1.9
						235	0.9
						360	1.1

Fig. 6 Onset of equilibrium by diameter and P value

References: [1] Cadogan P. H. (2024) *Icarus*, 408 [2]. Oberst L. et al.(2012) *PSS* 74 179-193 [3] Le Feuvre M. and Wieczorek M. A. (2011) *Icarus* 214 1-20. [4] Fassett C.I et al. (2022) *JGR Planets* 127. [5] Hiesinger H. et al. (2012) *JGR* 117 [6] Arvidson R, et al (1976) *PLSC* 7 2817-2832 [7] Bogert C. H. v d et al *LPSC* 43 Abstract 1847 [8] Hartman W.K. (1984) *Icarus* 60 56-74